

**Randomised Controlled Trials of Interventions in Acute Kidney Injury in
Critical Illness: Protocol for a scoping review**

Supplement

Search strategy

The search uses the Cochrane Collaboration's highly sensitive filter for RCTs.(1) We restricted searches to studies published during or after May 2004. Full OVID Medline search terms are included below. We searched Clinical Trials (www.ClinicalTrials.gov) using the terms: Acute Kidney Injury, and then filtered results for interventional studies.

1 *Acute Kidney Injury/*

2 *acute kidney injury.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]*

3 *AKI.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]*

4 *acute kidney failure.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]*

5 *acute renal failure.mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]*

6 *or/1-5*

7 *exp randomized controlled trial/*

8 *controlled clinical trial.pt.*

9 *randomized.ab.*

- 10 *placebo.ab.*
- 11 *drug therapy.fs.*
- 12 *randomly.ab.*
- 13 *trial.ab.*
- 14 *groups.ab.*
- 15 *7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14*
- 16 *exp animals/ not humans.sh.*
- 17 *15 not 16*
- 18 *6 and 17*
- 19 *limit 18 to yr="2004 -Current"*

<https://ovidsp.ovid.com/athens/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&NEWS=N&PAGE=main&SHAREDSEARCHID=46kY6kgPOPyP2trXsFZmS1b4Esbz5uzP5ZpIR3BBs74SEUJ4o2CHdpQuNT28mrP0b>

Data Extraction Forms

We will use three data extraction forms: one for general trial data (1 row per trial), one for outcomes (1 row per outcome), and one for participant characteristics

Extraction for trial level data:

trial id	Initials of extractor	Notes	Doi	Journal	Author/trial acronym	Year	Countries	Number of centres

Number of patients	AKI definition	AKI time	biomarker	Patient subgroup	Enrichment [y/n]	Enrichment type

Intervention design [prevention/treatment/attenuation]	Intervention type [drug/management/crrt]	Interventions	Full protocol available and referenced [y/n]

Extraction form for outcome level data:

Trial id	Initials of extractor	Outcome #	Outcome	Definition/tool used	Type [mortality / AKI / kidney non-mortality / ICU non-mortality]	Baseline definition	Composite outcome [y/n]	Prioritization of multiple outcome components [NR if not relevant]

Assessment time point incl. censoring/truncation	Death - proportion [n/N - %]	Handling of death	Missing data - proportion [n/N - %]	Missing data handling strategy	Effect measure(s) used	Statistical analysis used

Extraction of participant characteristics

Trial id	Initials of extractor	Place of residence	Race	Ethnicity	Culture	Language	Occupation	Gender	Sex	Social capital

PRISMA-ScR Checklist.

Completed PRISMA-ScR checklist for this protocol.NA: not applicable (several items are not applicable during the protocol stage).(2)

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	3,4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	4
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	4
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	5,6
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	4
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	5 and supplement
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	5 and supplement
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was	supplement

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
		done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	supplement
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	NA
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	7
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	NA
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	NA
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	NA
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	NA
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	NA
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	7,8
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	8
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	8
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	8

JBI = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (6) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JBI guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMAScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169:467–473. doi: [10.7326/M18-0850](https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850).

1. 4.S1 Technical Supplement to Chapter 4: Searching for and selecting studies [Internet]. [cited 2024 Apr 8]. Available from: <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-04-technical-supplement-searching-and-selecting-studies>
2. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med*. 2018 Oct 2;169(7):467–73.